

**FEATURES OF TRANSLATION OF GASTRONOMIC FRAGMENTS IN
THE BELLES LETTRES**
(A Comparative Study of Russian and English Literature)

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Annotation. *The article considers the features of translation of gastronomic fragments in belles lettres. It analyzes excerpts of text related to food. The article presents the texts of culinary recipes, which indicate: names of kitchen utensils; names of ingredients, seasonings; terms for cutting, processing and cooking; method of preparation; vocabulary indicating number of components. Excerpts from literary works, their translations and translation rules followed by the translators are given.*

Keywords. *Discourse, gastronomy, speech, works of art, food, kitchen, dialogue, monologue, fragment.*

Introduction. The text of belles lettres differs from the text of a culinary recipe, it is not limited by a structural framework. The writers depict everyday scenes of eating, as well as rituals and festive ceremonies. The author of the work must follow the traditions and peculiarities of the described time, the class of the characters in the work and the place of events.

The translation of gastronomic fragments in literary work is a complex and multifaceted process that requires consideration of both linguistic and cultural characteristics. Food in literature often acts not only as an element of the narrative, but also as a symbol reflecting the social status, national identity or emotional state of the characters. The present article is aimed at studying the peculiarities of the translation of gastronomic fragments in pairs of Russian and English languages, with an emphasis on preserving the cultural context and literary style.

Literature analysis and methodology. Gastronomic fragments in literature have long attracted the attention of researchers, as they play an important role in creating an atmosphere and revealing characters. In Russian literature, for example, bread and salt symbolize hospitality and friendship, which requires a special approach when translating into English, where such symbols may be less understandable. In English literature, on the contrary, descriptions of food often focus on details, creating visual and sensory images, as seen in the works of Virginia Woolf. Texts by Russian and English authors in which gastronomic fragments play a significant role were selected for the analysis. The works of Sergei Task (*The Secret of the Red Cat*) and N.V.Gogol (*Dead Souls*) were considered as examples from

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Russian literature. Texts by Oscar Wilde (*Portrait of Dorian Gray*) and Agatha Christie (*Murder Declared*) were analyzed from English literature. The methodology included a comparative analysis of the original texts and their translations, with an emphasis on preserving cultural and literary features.

Results. The analysis showed that the translation of gastronomic fragments requires the use of different strategies depending on the context. In addition, there have been cases where translators have encountered difficulties in conveying cultural realities. For example, the Russian expression "хлеб и соль" (bread and salt) is often left untranslated with an explanation in a footnote in order to preserve the cultural context.

The subject of the discourse is all the characters dealing with cooking, eating or serving in a cafe, restaurant, etc. The gastronomic discourse of belles lettres differs in that the speech situations there are fictional, they are a figment of the writer's imagination, while the recipes in the book actually took place.

A culinary recipe can be on the pages of a work of art, but the author forms it in the general plane of the entire text. According to many readers, thematically, texts about food are sometimes divided according to the principle that women writers often write about baking (for example, Agatha Christie), and men – about meat. Interesting recipes and cooking tips can be found in detective stories and thrillers. We will give examples of recipes for dishes that are found in literary work and have become popular. The author of the books, Agatha Christie, loved to eat delicious food and adored sweets, so, in the work "Murder Declared," the Delicious Death cake is presented - a whipped soufflé with liqueur and meringues. Dick Francis in the novel "Dead heat" gave a recipe for "Beef Stroganoff". Following the canons of gastronomic discourse, the authors of the works realistically presented descriptions and even cooking techniques, so that the followers of their work published cookbooks of dozens of recipes that were loved by Miss Marple, Poirot (Agatha Christie) and Albert Hitchcock characters.

The inner monologue of the character allows you to reveal the motivation of actions and character. The dialogue of gastronomic discourse is a conversation between fictional participants, the addresser and the addressee of culinary communication, here is an example of a fragment from the book "The Secret of the Red Cat":

Russian: «...мороженая клюква с сахаром, заливные орехи, засахаренный миндаль, горох моченый, бублики и сайки, изюм кувшинный, пастила рябиновая, постный сахар - лимонный, малиновый, с апельсинчиками внутри, халва... А

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жареная гречневая каша с луком, запить квасом! А постные пирожки с грудями, а гречневые блины с луком по субботам... а кутья с мармеладом в первую субботу, какое-то «коливо»!»

English translation: *«frozen cranberries with sugar, jellied nuts, candied almonds, soaked peas, bagels and saika, jug raisins, rowan marshmallow, lean sugar - lemon, raspberry, with oranges inside, halva ... And fried buckwheat porridge with onions, drink kvass! BUT meatless pies with mushrooms, and buckwheat pancakes with onions on Saturdays ... and kutya with marmalade on the first Saturday, some kind of «kolivo»!*

Using the example of this passage, we will give an example that a monologue or dialogue may also include menu items. The menu, partially or completely, can be presented on the pages of the literary work, but it will be designed as part of the overall text. Gastronomic discourse is associated with episodes of eating, as well as with any situations related to gastronomy. When translating menus and recipe names in the content of fiction books, the translator must follow the rules for translating plaintext and culinary text. The translated version of the menu and the culinary recipe should preserve the atmosphere of the era, show the popular dishes of the time when the events of the literary work take place.

The gastronomic discourse is defined by the gastronomic vocabulary: the names of food objects, dishes; the names of utensils; the names of the process of eating; the time of eating; the place of eating.

The features of the literary text make it possible to see gastronomic situations in natural everyday moments, but they are limited by the scope of the artistic work. The situation can be influenced by the participants of the discourse, the time, place and style of the author, so the translator needs to pay attention to these factors, as well as take into account cultural and gastronomic peculiarities, culinary variations of countries can lead to misunderstandings or inaccuracies in translation.

To analyze the Russian-English translation, we took excerpts from the narrative by N.V. Gogol's "Dead Souls" in the translations of D.J.Hogarth and Christopher English, the text is replete with culinary texts typical of Russia of that era, the translator's task is not to lose the semantic load of the original. In addition to describing the dishes, the author has added subtle remarks to culinary preferences that give an understanding of the character's nature, which complicates the translator's work.

Gastronomic discourse can be presented both at home and in a public place, the translation of "кафе, ресторан, трактир, паб, закусочная, бар, кошерная,

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пельменная, блинная, буфет, café, restaurant, pub, bar" depends on the nationality of the discourse.

Of course, the most interesting thing is the translation of gastronomic units, since they are the ones that cause difficulty in translation. In this case, we will consider ways to convey the purpose of the utterance, grammatical and stylistic features of the fragment transmission.

When translating Oscar Wilde's novel "The Portrait of Dorian Gray", the translator often used lexical-grammatical transformations, for example, combining two simple sentences into one complex, the position of the described people and their actions are concretized. The phrasal verb *went over* was replaced with "встал" (*got up*) - concretization, *poured out the tea* –replacement with "занялся чаем", *the two men* – concretization to "остальные двое" (the other two) and grammatical replacement of part of speech, *a covers* (крышка, покрытие) [Cambridge dic.] – "стеклянные колпаки блюд" – a descriptive translation was applied with the addition of the clarification *glass* (стеклянный) – lexical-grammatical transformations.

"Please have", which can be translated as "угощайтесь" (*help yourself*), the second translation uses the phrase "This is". The wordplay principle in translation is expressed in the use of transformations at both syntactic and semantic levels to preserve the pragmatics of the text and convey the meaning of the text to the reader.

Discussion. The results of the study emphasize the importance of taking cultural differences into account when translating gastronomic fragments. In Russian literature, food is often associated with national identity and traditions, which requires a translator to have a deep understanding of the cultural context. In English literature, the emphasis on detail and sensory imagery requires maintaining stylistic accuracy.

Translators use various strategies, including:

- **Loan translation:** saving the original name of the dish with an explanation (for example, "борщ - borscht" (beetroot and cabbage soup)).
- **Adaptation:** replacing a dish with a similar one in the translation culture.
- **Descriptive translation:** explanation of ingredients and cooking method.

Each of these strategies has its advantages and disadvantages, and the choice of approach depends on the context and the target audience.

Conclusion. The translation of gastronomic fragments in belles lettres is a complex task that requires consideration of both linguistic and cultural characteristics. An analysis of Russian and English texts has shown that successful

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translation depends on the translator's ability to preserve the cultural context and literary style of the original. Future research may focus on examining readers' perceptions of such translations and developing new strategies to convey cultural realities.

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